

A volunteer perspective

Nigel Nolan and Ian Smith - Question and answer session

Davina Bonner: I'm just wondering from you both whether you get more out of working on ongoing large projects, or more specific tasks, and not routine maintenance?

Ian Smith: I like both. You're not doing something [big] always on something. All right, the Hunslet was virtually a nine-month project and that was based here. But since I've finished the Hunslet I've been on other little projects and I enjoy them. As I say I try to take a positive out of all the little jobs, even if it's only changing oil you know? That might sound silly but I do try to take a positive out of all the jobs, and that way then I feel that I have done something, you know? Something worthwhile you know?

Nigel Nolan: Yeah, I think you need to realize that you can't be working on big projects all the time, that the maintenance has to be done and that it's important, so do it well, basically.

Ian Smith: It's like I said, it's like a big jigsaw puzzle. And the whole year when your whole program rotates, it turns out to be like a big picture you know?